

Health Effects of Micro- and Nanoplastics

Executive Summary

Micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs), ubiquitous byproducts of global plastic pollution, pose significant potential risks to human health. These particles, often smaller than 5 mm, are increasingly found in food, water, air, and human tissues. Research underscores their ability to traverse biological barriers, accumulate in organs, and disrupt cellular and systemic functions. MNPs raise concerns about long-term adverse health effects. This 3rd PlasticsFatE policy brief examines current findings on MNP exposure pathways, biological interactions, and potential health impacts, emphasizing the urgent need for policy interventions to mitigate possible risks.

Introduction

Embedded within the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme, several interdisciplinary research initiatives aim to deepen our understanding of how MNPs and their additives affect human health. Recent studies by Luo et al. (2022), Monikh et al. (2022), Kokalj et al. (2023), Ramsperger et al. (2023), Schvartz et al. (2023), Tamargo et al. (2022), and Wieland et al. (2024) highlight how environmental exposure to MNPs occurs, elucidating key routes of human contact. Given the increasing ubiquity of MNPs, investigating their presence in the human body is critical. These particles have been detected in various human tissues, including the lungs, placenta, liver, spleen, kidneys (Roslan et al., 2024), urine (Rotchell et al., 2024), blood (Leslie et al., 2022) and brain (Nihart et al., 2025). Their ability to induce cellular stress and inflammation raises significant concerns regarding long-term health implications.

Research on health effects of MNPs is pivotal not only for understanding acute risks but also for informing future regulatory frameworks and enhancing safety measures related to chronic MNP exposure. As considerable knowledge gaps remain regarding the hazard potential of MNPs, the most effective precautionary measures involve reducing emissions and limiting human exposure to this complex class of persistent pollutants.

Health Impacts

1. Immune System Dysregulation

MNPs trigger immune system reactions primarily through their interaction with immune cells, such as macrophages. When macrophages phagocytize (internalize) these particles, they produce pro-inflammatory cytokines and reactive oxygen species (ROS), leading to chronic inflammation. Over time, this can impair the immune system's capacity to respond effectively to infections and may contribute to autoimmune disorders. Evidence highlights reduced phagocytic activity in macrophages exposed to MNPs, compromising their pathogen-clearing ability and exacerbating systemic inflammation (Adler et al., 2024; Wieland et al., 2022). Importantly, associated chemicals—including plastic additives and environmental pollutants—likely play a critical role in these immune disruptions, though their full impact on MNP hazards is only beginning to be understood (Cheng et al., 2024; Yang et al., 2022).

2. Respiratory and Cardiovascular Effects

Inhalation of airborne MNPs, such as those derived from urban dust and synthetic textiles, can cause significant damage to respiratory tissues. Depending on their size, these particles can penetrate deep into the lungs, inducing oxidative stress, inflammation, and fibrosis in alveolar regions. Long-term exposure to MNPs is associated with other chronic respiratory conditions like asthma and bronchitis. Additionally, MNPs may enter the circulatory system, potentially contributing to cardiovascular diseases such as atherosclerosis by interacting with endothelial cells and promoting systemic inflammation (Jiménez-Arroyo et al., 2023; Marfella et al., 2024; Prattichizzo et al., 2024; Schwartz et al., 2023).

Emerging evidence suggests that the risks associated with micro- and nanoplastics may extend beyond the particles themselves to the chemicals and biocontaminants they can transport. This Trojan Horse effect—although still the subject of an ongoing scientific debate—raises concerns about the potential for harmful substances to enter the body, accumulate in organs, and trigger physiological responses (Carriera et al., 2023; Koelmans et al., 2022).

3. Gastrointestinal and Microbiome Disruption

MNP ingestion, primarily through contaminated food, food contact material, and water, poses significant risks to gastrointestinal health. These particles can adhere to intestinal surfaces, disrupt epithelial barriers, and alter the gut microbiota. Disruption of microbial diversity (dysbiosis) has been linked to metabolic disorders, increased intestinal permeability (“leaky gut”), and systemic inflammation. Simulated digestion studies indicate that MNPs promote bacterial biofilm formation and interact with gut microbes, potentially leading to shifts in metabolic profiles and impaired gut functionality (Jiménez-Arroyo et al., 2023; Tamargo et al., 2022).

Given that MNPs can adsorb both chemical pollutants and microbial contaminants, their combined effects on gut health remain an urgent area of research (Tamargo et al., 2022).

4. Long-Term and Systemic Risks

The presence of MNPs in human tissues, such as the liver, kidneys, and even the brain, raises concerns about chronic toxicity. Long-term exposure may increase the risk of carcinogenicity, neurotoxicity, and reproductive health issues (Barboza et al., 2020; Ramsperger et al., 2023).

Although definitive human studies are scarce, animal research underscores the potential for MNP-induced hormonal imbalances, fertility challenges, and neuroinflammation, necessitating further investigation (Jeong et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2024).

For all four types of health risks described above, the possible contribution of MNP-associated chemicals and biological contaminants must also be considered. However, elucidating the contribution of physical, chemical and biological toxicity to the overall effect of MNPs remains an important task for future research.

There are still many questions in this context, including the strength of an exposure-increasing vector effect of MNP for chemicals, which is still the subject of controversial debate (Gouin & Whelan, 2024; Koelmans et al., 2022).

The following graphic summarizes key insights:

Figure 1: Possible health impacts of exposure to MNPs
 Source: Own creation, based on the literature mentioned in this Policy Brief

Summary

The increasing presence of MNPs in the environment and human body underscores their potential to pose significant health risks. These particles infiltrate various bodily systems through ingestion, inhalation, and dermal exposure, affecting immune responses, respiratory and cardiovascular health, gastrointestinal function, and long-term systemic well-being.

Research highlights their role in inducing inflammation, disrupting microbiota, and interfering with endocrine functions, raising concerns about chronic conditions such as cardiovascular disease, metabolic disorders, and potential neurotoxicity (Jiménez-Arroyo et al., 2023).

Findings from the **PlasticsFatE** project indicate that while studies on pristine MNPs have shown limited acute effects, MNPs associated with chemicals or biocontaminants cause more pronounced effects in biological systems, including alterations in gene expression, further increasing their potential health risks (see e.g. Adler et al., 2024)

Further Research Needed

Despite increasing awareness of the overall exposure and potential risks posed by micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs), substantial knowledge gaps remain. Future research should focus on

- **Toxicokinetics and Bioaccumulation:** Determining how MNPs are absorbed, distributed, metabolized, and excreted in the human body.
- **Longitudinal Human Studies:** Establishing large-scale epidemiological studies to assess the long-term health effects of chronic MNP exposure.
- **Interaction with Human Microbiota:** Investigating how MNPs alter gut, lung, and skin microbiomes and their role in disease development.
- **Synergistic Effects:** Investigating whether and how MNPs enhance the transport and bioavailability of additives, chemical pollutants, and pathogens, which could potentially increase the toxicity and immune-disrupting potential of MNPs.
- **Microbial Interactions:** Investigating the potential of adsorbed biofilms and toxins on MNPs to cause or exacerbate inflammation, gut dysbiosis, and systemic health risks.
- **Standardized Detection Methods:** Developing harmonized methodologies for quantifying MNPs in biological samples and environmental media.¹

Understanding these aspects is critical for informing future regulations, improving public health care strategies, and mitigating the risks associated with MNP exposure.

Implications for EU and National Policy: Blind Spots and Recommendations

1. **Monitoring and Risk Assessment:**
 - a. **Standardized Protocols:** Develop uniform methods for detecting and quantifying MNPs in various media, including food, water, and air.
 - b. **Longitudinal Studies:** Fund long-term epidemiological research to evaluate the health effects of chronic MNP exposure.
 - c. **Vulnerable Populations:** Prioritize studies on populations at higher risk, such as children, pregnant women, and those with chronic illnesses.
 - d. **Exposure Characterization:** Improve the detection methods for the assessment of nanoplastics and particle-associated chemicals in environmental and occupational settings.
2. **Public Awareness and Education:**
 - a. **Consumer Guidance:** Educate the public on reducing exposure through lifestyle changes, such as avoiding single-use plastics or using water filters.
 - b. **Corporate Responsibility:** Encourage businesses to minimize plastic footprints through sustainable packaging and circular waste management practices.
3. **International Collaboration:**
 - a. **Global Agreements:** Establish international treaties to address plastic pollution, focusing on transboundary impacts of MNPs.
 - b. **Shared Databases:** Create repositories for research data to facilitate global collaboration and knowledge exchange.

¹ For more details on the need for harmonization and standardization in plastic exposure assessment, refer to the 1st PlasticsFatE policy brief: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14972006> (Steffens et al., 2025)

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